

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF THE HIGH STRAIN RATE BEHAVIOR OF S-2 GLASS/VINYL ESTER COMPOSITES UNDER COMPRESSIVE LOADING

Hassan Mahfuz, Bazle A. Gama, Roshan P. Raines and Shaik Jeelani

*Tuskegee University's Center for Advanced Materials (T-CAM), Tuskegee University,
Tuskegee, Alabama 36088, USA*

SUMMARY: Transient dynamic Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of the high strain rate behavior of S-2 Glass/Vinyl Ester composites under compressive loading is performed at a maximum strain rate of 1700 s^{-1} . The stress propagation and distribution through the specimen with respect to time are presented. The stress contours show the distribution of stress through the specimen and also identify the location of maximum stresses. In the initial stage of loading, in the thickness direction, the FEA prediction of the stress-strain behavior correlates well with the experiment. However, for the fill direction loading the correlation is not as good. For both cases, the normal stresses in the thickness direction are found to be alternately compressive and tensile with respect to time. The interlaminar shear stresses also change their sign with time. This alternating nature of stresses with respect to time occurs much earlier in the case of fill direction loading. Experimental observation and FEA in the case of thickness direction loading show that compressive failure initiates at the transmission face of the specimen in the initial stage, which is followed by delamination in the later stage. During fill direction loading, however, fiber buckling, edge cracks and disintegration of the specimen have been observed to be the dominant failure modes.

KEYWORDS: finite element, high strain rate, S-2 glass, vinyl ester, compressive loading

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, composite structures subjected to high strain rate dynamic loading have become a subject of great interest to various defense and commercial industries. High strain loading may arise in different ways. High speed automotive crash, a flying bird's impact to an airplane wing, ballistic penetration and explosive shock impact to static and moving structures are a few examples. Due to the higher strength to weight ratio over metals, composite materials are being used more as structural materials, both in aerospace and defense industries. One such application is the Composite Armored Vehicle (CAV), which is being developed by the U.S. Army. The main load bearing component of the upper hull is the thick section S-2 Glass/Vinyl Ester which experiences shock loading in the event of a ballistic impact at the external ceramic layers. It is imperative that the procedures to test these materials at high strain rate be fully developed and their response be completely understood through analytical and experimental approaches.

Sufficient work has been done on high strain rate testing of metals [1, 2 and 3]; however, a limited amount of work has been done on high strain rate testing of composite materials [4, 5, 6, 7 and 8]. One of the pioneers of this field, Nemat-Nasser [9, 10 and 11], has developed several Hopkinson bar experimental techniques. The stress-reversal momentum trap version of the compression split Hopkinson bar allows dynamic recovery experiments. The development of the tension split Hopkinson bar, copper pulse shaping, and several gas gun systems for plate impact and penetration experiments are some of the achievements, along with analytical and numerical modeling. Staab and Gilat [6] have used a tensile version of the Hopkinson bar to measure the rate dependent response of angle ply S-2 Glass composites. Dandekar, Green and Beaulieu [8] studied the effect of S-2 Glass/Polyester composites specimen geometry in quasi-static and medium strain rates. They found failure strains of S-2 Glass reinforced plastics to be much higher in the thickness direction than in the fill direction. Leber and Lifshitz [12] designed a new type of specimen for the static and high strain rate interlaminar shear behavior of plain-weave fiber reinforced laminates. They used the torsion split Hopkinson bar for experiment and modeled the experiment with Finite Element Methods. They found that the E-Glass/Epoxy material exhibits high sensitivity to the loading rate in respect to shear modulus, fracture strength and strain. Other researchers [13 and 14] used DYNA3D to model the composite material subjected to impact and/or high strain rate loading and used their material model to analyze the failure.

HOPKINSON BAR EXPERIMENTS

The FEA is based on Hopkinson bar experiments performed at Tuskegee University's Center for Advanced Materials (T-CAM). The material used for the experiments is plain weave S-2 Glass/Vinyl Ester composite, fabricated using the SCRIMP process. Test specimens are 8.89 mm (0.35 inch) square in cross-section, 8.23 mm (0.324 inch) in thickness and have 12 layers along the thickness. The test apparatus is a compression split Hopkinson bar with a momentum trap. Its incident and transmitter bars are each 1.524 meters (5 feet) long, with a diameter of 19.05 mm (0.75 inch), used in conjunction with a 228.6 mm (9 inch) striker bar.

Two different loading conditions are used, one in the thickness direction and the other in the fill direction of the composite specimens. The average strain rate in the thickness direction was 850 s^{-1} , and that in the fill direction was 1280 s^{-1} . Figure 1 shows examples of experimental stress vs. strain curves for both loading conditions (two specimens for each condition). The initial moduli of elasticity shown in the figure are the average values from the two test specimens for the corresponding loading condition. For the fill direction loading these values are much higher than the through thickness loading. This can be attributed to the fact that the material response is matrix dominated through the thickness and fiber dominated in the fill direction. The through thickness direction loaded specimens sustained higher stresses (as much as 640 MPa) and failure strains (approximately 10%) compared to specimens loaded in the fill direction, with maximum stresses of approximately 345 MPa and failure strains of about 1%. Figure 2 shows corresponding stress vs. time curves for the same specimens. Here, the time span from initial loading to failure is much greater through the thickness than in the fill direction. Both figures show that the responses for the two loading conditions are distinctively different from each other, and specimens loaded under the same conditions follow the same basic pattern, showing good repeatability.

Fig. 1: Stress-Strain behavior of S-2 Glass/Vinyl Ester Composites

Fig. 2: Stress-Time curves for S-2 Glass/Vinyl Ester Composite

Several specimens were tested to establish the baseline data for FEA. Figures 3 and 4 are the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) micrographs for specimens loaded through the thickness and in the fill direction, respectively. These figures show that delamination due to interlaminar tension, and matrix cracks are the dominating failure modes in the through thickness loading. However, failure in the form of fiber buckling, edge cracks, matrix cracks and fiber breakage are dominant modes in the fill direction loading.

Fig. 3: SEM Micrographs for Loading in the Thickness Direction a) Matrix Crack b) & c) Delamination due to Interlaminar Tension d) Matrix Crack

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

In the current investigation, transient dynamic FEA is performed to model the high strain rate behavior of S-2 Glass/Vinyl Ester composites under compressive loading. Layered 3D solid elements (SOLID46) have been used to model the composite specimens. The element SOLID46 is based on the lamination theory, which considers the strain distribution in the thickness direction to be constant. Several elements through the thickness direction are employed in the FEA model to compensate for the non-linearity of strain along the thickness. Quasi-static properties of the laminate are used in the finite element program. The properties of the specimens, geometry, and FEA model are presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 4: SEM Micrographs for Loading in the Fill Direction a) Edge Crack b) & c) Matrix Crack d) Fiber Breakage

Fig. 5: Specimen Geometry, FEA model and Properties.

Time dependent loading similar to experiments is applied on the model as a distributed force on the loading surfaces. To simulate the experiment, the nodes on the surface of loading are coupled together to enforce equal displacement of all nodes on that surface. The displacement of the nodes opposite to the surface of loading is constrained in the direction of loading

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Loading in the Thickness Direction

Figure 6 shows the loading in the thickness direction. The comparison of the stress-strain response between experiment and FEA is presented in Figure 7. The FEA prediction of initial modulus is about 17% less than the experimental modulus. The correlation between experiment and FEA is good in the initial stage of loading. The FEA is unable to predict the post-yielding behavior of the material, because the stress calculation is based on linear elasticity.

Fig. 6: Loading and Boundary Conditions, Thickness Direction.

Fig. 7: Comparison of Stress-Strain Behavior between Experiment and FEA

The stress contours of the FEA model with respect to time have been analyzed to determine the location of maximum stresses. Contour plots of σ_z and τ_{xz} are presented in Figure 8, which show that the maximum σ_z occurs at $X/W1 = 0.5$ and the maximum τ_{xz} occurs at $X/W1 = 0.3$ and at 0.7 along the thickness. These locations are used to see the variation of different stresses with respect to time. The variation of σ_z (interlaminar normal stress) and τ_{xz} (interlaminar shear stress) with time are shown in figures 9 and 10 (at $X/W1 = 0.5$). The variation of σ_z is fluctuating in nature and becomes tensile at times 175.0×10^{-6} second and 230.0×10^{-6} second. Though the applied load was compressive, these interlaminar tensile stresses are tensile and may cause delamination in the specimen. Also, τ_{xz} changes its sign with time and becomes considerably high at times 175.0×10^{-6} , 205.0×10^{-6} and 230.0×10^{-6}

second. The interlaminar shear strength obtained through short beam shear test (ASTM D: 2344-84 (89)) is 27.66 MPa (4012 psi), which is more than twice the maximum τ_{xz} of 12.4 MPa. However, together with the interlaminar tensile stress, interlaminar shear stress can cause delamination and matrix crack opening.

The through thickness distributions of σ_z and τ_{xz} are plotted in Figures 11 and 12 at different time steps in the location of maximum interlaminar shear. In the initial stage of loading (at time 50.0×10^{-6} second), σ_z is compressive in nature, and the value is about 640 MPa at the bottom face of the specimen. From the experimental stress-time curve (Fig. 2), we can see that the failure stress is about 640 MPa at time 130.0×10^{-6} second. It is evident that the failure at the transmission (bottom) face initiates at 50.0×10^{-6} second and continues till 130.0×10^{-6} second. At time 175.0×10^{-6} second σ_z is tensile and is minimum (11.7 MPa) on the loading face and maximum (317 MPa) on the opposite face of the specimen. The tensile strength of the Vinyl Ester matrix is 69-82 MPa (10000-12000 psi). Therefore, matrix cracks and delamination will occur in the range of $0 < Z/L < 0.68$ along the thickness.

The τ_{xz} distribution shows two different peak locations, at $Z/L = 0.33$ and 0.67 , which suggests that delamination is likely to occur at these locations. The maximum value of τ_{xz} (15.85 MPa) is much less than the interlaminar shear strength (27.66 MPa) of the specimen. However, τ_{xz} alone can not cause delamination. From this observation we conclude that compressive failure initiates at the bottom face of the specimen in the initial stage, followed by delamination in the later stages of loading

Fig. 8: Contours of (a) Normal Stress (σ_z), (b) Interlaminar Shear Stress (τ_{xz})

Fig. 9: Variation of Normal Stress (σ_z) with Time

Fig. 10: Variation of Shear Stress (τ_{xz}) with Time

Fig. 11: Normal Stress (σ_z) Distribution Along Thickness in Different Time Step

Fig. 12: Shear Stress (τ_{xz}) Distribution Along Thickness in Different Time Step

Loading in the Fill Direction

Figure 13 shows the loading in the fill direction. The comparison of the stress-strain response between experiment and FEA is presented in Figure 14. The FEA prediction of initial modulus is about 64% less than the experimental modulus. The correlation between experiment and FEA is not as good as in the case of the thickness direction loading. The reason for such discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that the constitutive equations used in the present investigation was limited to linear elasticity. During the pressure pulse loading one has to consider the separation of the thermodynamic response from the ability of the materials to convey shear loads. This calls for the modification of the constitutive equation and the equation of state. These modifications will be incorporated in future work.

Fig. 13: Loading and Boundary Conditions, Fill Direction

Fig. 14: Comparison of Stress-Strain Behavior between Experiment and FEA

Contour plots of σ_z and τ_{xz} at time 20.0×10^{-6} second are presented in Figure 15, which show that the maximum σ_z occur at $Z/L = 0.33$ and at 0.67 , and the maximum τ_{xz} occurs at $X/W1 = 0.7$ along the thickness. These locations are used to see the variation of different stresses with respect to time.

The variation of σ_z (interlaminar normal stress) and τ_{xz} (interlaminar shear stress) with time are shown in figures 16 and 17 (at $X/W1 = 0.5$). The plot of σ_z indicates that from the early stage of loading it alternately becomes tensile and compressive. However, the maximum interlaminar tensile stress never exceeds 35 MPa. Compared to the tensile strength of the matrix (69-82 MPa) this interlaminar tensile stress will not cause delamination. Interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} , changes its sign with time from the very beginning. The maximum value is about 25 MPa. As compared to the experimental interlaminar shear strength of 27.66 MPa, the FEA prediction suggests no delamination. However, the repeated action of interlaminar tension and shear may cause stress concentration around any embedded flaw in the specimen and can cause delamination and matrix crack opening.

The through thickness distributions of σ_z and τ_{xz} are plotted in Figures 18 and 19 at different time steps in the location of maximum interlaminar shear. The locations of maximum interlaminar tensile stress are found to be at $Z/L = 0.33$ and 0.67 . The maximum interlaminar tension (50 MPa) occurred at time 25.0×10^{-6} second. The plot of interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} , shows that the maximum shear stress (25 Mpa) occurs either at the incident (top) or transmission face of the specimen, which suggests that delamination and edge cracks may occur at these places. With the combined effect of interlaminar tensile and shear stress, the most possible locations for delamination are at $Z/L = 0.33$ and at 0.67 .

Fig. 15: Contours of (a) Normal Stress (σ_z), (b) Interlaminar Shear Stress (τ_{xz})

Fig. 16: Variation of Normal Stress (σ_z) with Time

Fig. 17: Variation of Shear Stress (τ_{xz}) with Time

Fig. 18: Normal Stress (σ_z) Distribution Along Thickness in Different Time Step

Fig. 19: Shear Stress (τ_{sz}) Distribution Along Thickness in Different Time Step

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are made from the high strain rate experiment and modeling of S-2 Glass/Vinyl Ester composites.

- FEA can only predict the initial stage of high strain rate deformation of composites.
- The FEA stress-strain behavior correlates well with experiment in the case of thickness direction loading.
- Compressive failure initiates at the transmission face of the specimen in the initial stage, followed by delamination in the later stage of loading in the thickness direction.
- Delamination occurs due to interlaminar tension and repeated interlaminar shear in the initial stage of loading in the fill direction.
- Fiber buckling, edge cracks and disintegration of the specimen along the thickness are observed in the case of fill direction loading.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The financial support for this work provided by the Army Research Office (ARO), USA, is gratefully acknowledged

REFERENCES

1. Lankford, J., Conque, A., Bose, A. and Anderson, C.E., "Microstructure Dependence of High-Strain-Rate Deformation and Damage Development in Tungsten Heavy Alloys", *Shock-Wave and High-Strain-Rate Phenomena in Materials*, edited by M. Meyers, L. Murr, K. Staudhammer, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1992, pp. 137-145.
2. Gabelotaud, S., Nguy, C., Bensussan, P., Berveiller, M., and Lipinski P., "High-Strain-Rate Titanium Compression Experimental Results and Modelization", *Shock-Wave and*

- High-Strain-Rate Phenomena in Materials*, edited by M. Meyers, L. Murr, K. Staudhammer, , Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1992, pp. 161-170.
3. Coates, R., Ramesh, K., "The Deformation of Tungsten Alloys at High Strain Rates", *Shock-Wave and High-Strain-Rate Phenomena in Materials*, edited by M. Meyers, L. Murr, K. Staudhammer, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1992, pp. 203-212.
 4. Harding, J., "Mechanical Behavior of Composite Materials Under Impact Loading", *Shock-Wave and High-Strain-Rate Phenomena in Materials*, edited by M. Meyers, L. Murr, K. Staudhammer, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1992, pp. 21-34.
 5. Newill, J. F. and Vinson, J. R., "Some High Strain Rate Effects on Composite Materials", *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM9)*, Madrid, 12-16 July, 1993, pp. 269-277.
 6. Staab, H. G. and Gilat, A., "High Strain Rate Characterization of Angle-Ply Glass/Epoxy Laminates", *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM9)*, Volume V, 1993, pp. 278-285.
 7. Harding, J. and Li, Y. L., "Determination of Interlaminar Shear Strength for Glass/Epoxy and Carbon/Epoxy at Impact Rates of Strain", *Composites Science and Technology*, 45, 1992, pp. 161-171.
 8. Dandekar, D. P., Green, J. L. And Beaulieu, P., "Dynamic Characterization", in *Dynamic Response of S-2 Glass Reinforced Plastic Structural Armor*, A Progress Report, ARL-SR-5, Army Research Laboratory, December 1993, pp. 39-62.
 9. Nemat-Nasser, S., Isaacs, J. B. And Starrett, J. E., "Hopkinson Techniques for Dynamic Recovery Experiments", *Proc. R. Soc. Lond., A*, 1991, 435, pp. 371-391.
 10. Nemat-Nasser, S., "New Frontiers in Dynamic Recovery Testing of Advanced Composites: Tailoring Microstructure for Optimal Performance", *JSME International Journal*, Series I, Vol. 34, No. 2, 1991, pp. 111-122.
 11. Nemat-Nasser, S., "Dynamic Deformation and Failure", High Strain Rate Effects on Polymer, Metals and Ceramic Matrix Composites and Other Advanced Materials, Edited by Y. Rajapakse, J. Vinson, ASME, U.S.A, 1995, pp. 371-391.
 12. Leber, H. and Lifshitz, J. M., "Interlaminar Shear Behavior of Plain-Weave GRP at Static and High Rates of Strain", *Composites Science and Technology*, 56, 1996, pp. 391-405.
 13. Kerth, S. and Maier., "Numerical Simulation of the Crashing of Composite Tubes", *Computer Aided Design in Composite Material Technology IV*, Editors: Blain, W. R. and DeWilde, W. P., 1994, pp. 141-148.
 14. Vinckier, D. and Thoma K., "Numerical Simulations High Velocity Impact Phenomena in Composite Structures", *Computer Aided Design in Composite Material Technology IV*, Editors: Blain, W. R. and DeWilde, W. P., 1994, pp. 183-190